

all three compounds indicates their structural similarity.

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Potentiometric Studies of Some Cerium(IV) and Dysprosium(III) Complexes

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THE present work was carried out to study the complexing properties of cerium(IV) and dysprosium(III) with 1-cyclohexyldene-2-benzylidene succinic acid (CHBSA), 1-cyclohexyldene succinic acid (CHSA), and 1-phenyl-3-thiobenzoyl thiocarbamide (PTT) at a fixed ionic strength and temperature. The communication reports for the first time the proton-ligand stability constants of all the three ligands and the metal-ligand stability constants of the complexes of CHBSA and CHSA with both cerium and dysprosium. The method used was the Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{1,2} as adapted by Irving and Rossotti³.

Experimental

Reagents: Stock solutions ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) of both cerium and dysprosium were prepared using ceric ammonium sulphate (AR, SM) and dysprosium chloride (Indian Rare Earths) in calculated quantity of perchloric acid solution to prevent hydrolysis.

All the three ligands, namely CHBSA⁴, CHSA⁴ and PTT^{5,6} were prepared and purified. The stock solutions ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) of CHBSA and CHSA were prepared in alcohol and PTT in acetone. The solutions of the ligands were prepared by suitable dilution of the stock solutions so that ligands were present in 30% alcoholic or acetone solution. The ligands solutions were standardized potentiometrically.

Sodium hydroxide pellets (EM) were dissolved in CO₂-free distilled water and kept overnight. A portion of it was diluted and its concentration determined by titrating it potentiometrically against standard potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.1M).

The stock solution of perchloric acid (EM) (0.1M) was prepared and standardized potentiometrically with a standard sodium hydroxide solution.

Potassium chloride (AnalaR) solution (1.0M) was used to maintain the ionic strength of the system and was prepared by dissolving a known weight in CO₂-free distilled water.

Apparatus: Elico pH meter (sensitivity ± 0.05) with glass-calomel electrode system was used for pH measurements. The pH meter was calibrated by a suitable buffer before use. All experiments were carried out at room temperature (27°).

Bjerrum-Calvin titration:

The three mixtures were prepared as follows: (A) 10 ml $10^{-1} M$ HClO₄ + 80 ml double distilled water + 10 ml M KCl solution, (B) 10 ml $10^{-1} M$ HClO₄ + 10 ml $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand solution + 20 ml redistilled acetone/alcohol + 10 ml M KCl solution + 50 ml double distilled water, and (C) 10 ml $10^{-1} M$ HClO₄ + 10 ml $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand solution + 20 ml redistilled acetone/alcohol + 10 ml $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal ion solution + 10 ml M KCl solution + 40 ml double distilled water. These solutions were titrated with a standard sodium hydroxide solution. The three curves obtained by plotting pH against the volume of alkali added were referred to as (a) acid titration curve, (b) ligand titration curve and (c) complex titration curve.

Results and Discussion

The calculation of practical proton ligand stability constant was carried out by plotting a graph of \bar{n}_A vs pH and applying the method of interpolation at half \bar{n}_A values and interpolation at various \bar{n}_A values. The values with error limit of ± 0.03 are given in Table I

TABLE 1—VALUES OF PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS

Ligands	Temp. = 27°		
	log K ₁ ^H	log K ₂ ^H	log B
CHBSA	7.46	5.03	12.49
CHSA	5.75	—	5.75
PTT	10.72	—	10.72

CHBSA has the following structure.

The formation curve of CHBSA extends from 0 to 2 on the \bar{n}_A scale indicating its dissociation as

CHSA has the following structure.

The formation curve of CHSA extends between 0 and 1 on the \bar{n}_A scale indicating its dissociation as

Although the molecule has two dissociable protons, only one value corresponding to log K₁^H could be obtained. It may be that the proton present as CH₂COOH dissociates immediately in the solution and its dissociation constant could not be studied in the present work.

PTT, a yet another analytically important reagent^{7,8} has the structure C₆H₅NH-C-NH-C-C₆H₅.

Its formation curve extends between 0 and 1 on the \bar{n}_A scale indicating its dissociation as

With the exception of PTT, in all other cases the complex titration curve (c) extends beyond the ligand titration curve (b). The metal ligand stability constants were calculated by the analysis of the formation curves obtained by plotting \bar{n} against pL. Various computational methods⁹ were applied to evaluate the stepwise formation constants. The error limits are ± 0.03 for log K₁ and ± 0.05 for log K₂. The mean values of concentration stability constants are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF CONCENTRATION STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES

Ligand	Temp. = 27°			Dy ^{III} system		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log B	log K ₁	log K ₂	log B
CHBSA	9.08	5.70	14.78	5.56	4.05	9.61
CHSA	—	3.45	—	—	2.85	—

Only one value is obtained in case of CHSA systems. The Ce^{IV}-PTT and Dy^{III}-PTT systems could not be studied as there was a precipitation beyond pH 3.0.

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Anion Exchange Separation of Some Metal Ions in Aqueous-Acetone-Dichloroacetic Acid Media. Part-III

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THE use of aqueous-acetone-carboxylic acid media has been shown for ion exchange separation of cations and successful multicomponent separations on anion exchange column were achieved^{1,2}. In continuation of our previous work in acetic and chloroacetic acid media, we have now examined the ion-exchange behaviour of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} on anion exchange resin in aqueous solutions of dichloroacetic acid (DCA) with varying concentrations from 0.5 to 3.0M at various percentages (0-80%) of acetone. The results, such as distribution coefficients and binary and tertiary mixture separations are reported.